

DEVELOPMENT OF QUESTIONNAIRE ON AWARENESS TOWARDS ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE-POWERED TOOLS

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to develop questionnaires on students' awareness towards Artificial Intelligence-powered tools. Simple random sampling technique employed to 1,050 college students who served as participants in the study. The results revealed a Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin and Bartlett's test of sphericity obtained 0.96 and significant p-value of .000 respectively, indicating that the sample size was marvelous and assumptions for conducting EFA were met. Conversely, suitability factor analysis shows a total of 35 items extracted from the initial pool of 70 questions. Identified factors comprised the Perception of AI Impact Factor 1 (12 items); Willingness to Adapt Factor 2 (10 items); Knowledge of AI-powered Tools Factor 3 (4 items); and Perceived Benefits Factor 4 (9 items). Overall Cronbach's Alpha and relative chi-square value of the entire questionnaire ranges from 0.82-0.92 and 1.735 fell within acceptable range. Furthermore, the TLI (0.945), CFI (0.951), IFI (0.951), and NFI (0.892) exceeded the 0.90 cutoff, indicating a good model fit. The RMSEA value of 0.039 suggested a superior fit compared to the recommended threshold of 0.08. In conclusion, the questionnaires effectively measured the investigated factors related to awareness of artificial intelligence-powered tools. Research suggests that questionnaires may be useful for those who have interest in AI-powered tools.

Keywords: *Artificial Intelligence Powered Tools, Perception of AI Impact, Willingness to Adapt, Knowledge of AI-powered Tools, Perceived Benefits*

INTRODUCTION

Artificial intelligence (AI) is an emulated human intelligence application capable of thinking, learning, and solving problems. AI applications have a transformative impact on the educational system that students use nowadays. In recent years, the field of Artificial Intelligence (AI) has witnessed rapid advancements, leading to its increasing integration into various aspects of our daily lives, including education. In late 2022 and early 2023, the public became aware of new generative AI chatbots. According to the US Department of Education (2023), it began exploring how AI could write essays, create lesson plans, produce images, and create individualized student assignments.

The survey questionnaire development aims to assess students' awareness of using the Artificial Intelligence (AI) powered tools in their future professions. It will focus on their familiarity with AI, their attitudes upon using it, and how AI dramatically affects a student's critical thinking to understand how Artificial Intelligence functions in this continuing new typical education. Renowned experts forecast the pivotal role that artificial intelligence technologies, such as ChatGPT, are destined to play as integral components of the educational landscape (Sharples, 2022). Moreover, the study seeks to develop a carefully crafted questionnaire, which will be a valuable resource for future researchers embarking on similar inquiries. This questionnaire will be developed to cover a vast array of AI-related topics and issues in the educational context, allowing future studies to assess AI awareness among college students with consistency and comparability.

Research Objective

This study generally aims to develop a questionnaire about students' awareness towards artificial intelligence particularly, the students of Central Mindanao University. The researchers specifically aim to attain the objective:

Develop a survey questionnaire determining students' awareness towards artificial intelligence powered tools.

METHODOLOGY

The researchers employed the quantitative research methodology. The study employs a descriptive survey research design that focuses on developing a research questionnaire that assesses students' awareness on their usage of AI software tools in the educational context. The study considered one thousand fifty (1,050) students from the Central Mindanao University colleges, and one hundred five (105) participants in each college will be chosen to answer the questionnaire. According to McMurtrie (2023), this employed the sampling size of 15:1 ratio, which implies that in a 70-item questionnaire,

there is a minimum sample size of one thousand fifty (1,050). Probability sampling was employed by researchers in this study.

The researchers developed a survey questionnaire which was composed of 70-item questions that had face and content validity by experts of the same field and was pilot-tested to the participants of this study with the permission of the College deans of and with the IERC approval. The study utilized Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity (Sürücü, n.d.). With this, Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) and Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) were utilized (Tavakol & Wetzel, 2020). In analyzing the data, the researchers had run through the data collected using R Programming Language to obtain descriptive statistics.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. KMO and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin	Measure of Sampling Adequacy (MSA)	0.96
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	χ^2	17188.14
	Df	2415
	p-value	.000*

*significant at $p \leq 0.05$

Table 1 presents the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy and Bartlett's test of sphericity. The KMO value of 0.96, based on a sample of 386 respondents, indicates excellent suitability for Exploratory factor analysis (EFA). Bartlett's test yielded a significant result ($p < .000^*$), confirming the appropriateness of the data for EFA. A non-significant result ($p > .05$) would suggest insufficient correlation among variables; this could necessitate either increasing the sample size or removing poorly correlating items before re-analyzing the data. If the result is different, it is recommended to increase the number of samples or remove the items that cause scattered correlation models from the analysis and perform factor analysis again (Sürücü, n.d.). Hence, all assumptions were met for EFA.

Parallel Analysis Scree Plots

Figure 1. Parallel Analysis Scree Plot

Figure 1 displays a parallel analysis scree plot, indicating a four-factor solution. This approach, employed to avoid under- or over factoring (which respectively hinder interpretation due to increased error and lead to overly complex models) as shown by the study of Mya et. al.(2021), shows the simulated eigenvalues crossing the observed eigenvalues between factors five and six, supporting the four-factor solution for the exploratory factor analysis (EFA). Factor loadings exceeding 0.30 represent a moderate correlation between an item and its factor.

In a sample size of (N=346), the researchers consider cross-factor loading and questions with the same mode to measure if both questions are similar, one must be omitted and the other must be retained.

EXPLORATORY FACTOR ANALYSIS

Table 2. Factor 1 (Perception of AI Impact)

Item No.	Item	Factor loading	Communalities
28	There are AI-powered virtual laboratories that provide students with realistic simulations and experiments.	0.55	0.373
32	AI can create customized digital portfolios for my academics.	0.74	0.543
34	AI can generate teaching materials tailored to specific subjects and grade levels.	0.74	0.534
35	AI can analyze students' reading habits and recommend subject-specific reading lists.	0.74	0.503

36	AI-driven note-taking tools can improve my study habits.	0.66	0.528
38	AI can aid in the development of adaptive educational games that accommodate various skill levels and learning styles.	0.79	0.571
39	AI is capable of analyzing the learning preferences of students and recommending courses or majors that correspond to their interests.	0.81	0.620
40	Complex math problems can be explained and solved instantly by AI for students.	0.61	0.466
41	AI can provide real-time language translation services for students participating in international online forums and discussions.	0.69	0.513
43	AI has the potential to transform how college students access and interact with educational content.	0.52	0.398
50	AI can help in my professional preparation and ability to keep up with technology advancements.	0.55	0.522
52	AI will be able to help me by giving me prompt feedback and direction on how my learning is progressing.	0.43	0.478

Factor 1, "Perception of AI Impact," comprises items (28, 32, 34, 35, 36, 38, 39, 40, 41, 43, 50 and 52) that have factor loading of (0.55, 0.74, 0.74, 0.74, 0.66, 0.79, 0.81, 0.61, 0.69, 0.52, 0.55 and 0.43), and has communalities of (0.373, 0.543, 0.534, 0.503, 0.528, 0.571, 0.620, 0.466, 0.513, 0.398, 0.522, and 0.478), respectively. The factor loadings indicate the strength of the relationship between each item and the underlying factor. Higher factor loadings suggest a stronger association between the item and the factor. For example, item 28 has a factor loading of 0.55, indicating a moderate positive relationship with the Perception of AI Impact factor.

Therefore, the resulting factor loading and communalities suggests that the Perception of AI Impact factor, as identified by the factor analysis, explains a substantial portion of the variance in these items.

Table 3. Factor 2 (Willingness to Adapt)

Item No.	Item	Factor loading	Communalities
54	I am open to receiving academic advising from AI-powered chatbots.	0.66	0.514
56	I actively search for news and updates regarding AI's role in education.	0.76	0.525
57	I am confident in my ability to navigate AI-powered platforms for academic purposes.	0.80	0.616
58	I am willing to receive academic advice from chatbots powered by artificial intelligence.	0.80	0.612

59	I am confident in my ability to distinguish between AI-generated content and human-generated content.	0.74	0.532
61	I am interested in using artificially intelligent systems in my daily life, especially in education.	0.76	0.578
62	I am impressed by what artificial intelligence can do	0.65	0.497
63	I rely on online sources like blogs, news stories, and instructional websites to broaden my knowledge about AI in education.	0.62	0.487
64	AI-powered tools enhance efficiency and productivity in tasks or activities.	0.70	0.557
65	I can list particular AI tools that are frequently applied in educational settings (such machine learning and natural language processing).	0.70	0.523

Factor 2 comprises ten items measuring willingness to adopt AI. Factor loadings (0.62–0.80) and communalities (0.487–0.616) indicate the suitability of these items for confirmatory factor analysis (CFA). Guadagnoli and Velicer (1988), as cited by Sürücü (n.d.), suggest that the necessary sample size in the existing literature primarily depends on the strength of the factors and items under study. The strong to moderate factor loadings suggest a substantial association between the items and Factor 2, implying that higher scores on these items reflect a greater willingness to adopt AI-powered tools in academic settings. The communalities further demonstrate that Factor 2 explains a significant portion of the variance in each item.

Table 4. Factor 3 (Knowledge of AI-powered Tools)

Item No.	Item	Factor loading	Communalities
1	there are AI powered-tools that are specifically designed for educational purposes.	0.68	0.693
2	there are concept of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in education.	0.85	0.707
3	AI-powered tools can enhance the learning experience for students	0.64	0.403
4	there are question-answering chatbots powered by AI used in education.	0.68	0.444

Factor 3, comprising four items (Items 1-4), assesses knowledge of AI-powered tools. These items demonstrate moderate to strong relationships with the factor, exhibiting factor loadings ranging from 0.64 to 0.85. Communalities, indicating the proportion of variance explained by the factor, range from 0.403 to 0.707, suggesting a substantial portion of each item's variance is accounted for by Factor 3. Based on multivariate statistical principles, factor loadings typically range from -1 to 1, with values closer to -1 or 1 signifying a stronger relationship between the variable and the factor.

The relatively high factor loadings and communalities of these items affirm their effectiveness in measuring the construct of knowledge about AI-powered tools.

Table 5. Factor 4 (Perceived Benefits)

Item No.	Item	Factor loading	Communalities
8	there are AI-powered content creation tools, such as automated essay generators or content summarizers, in action.	0.69	0.414
9	AI algorithms are being used in college to detect and prevent academic dishonesty and cheating.	0.63	0.348
10	there are AI-powered tools for developing interactive and engaging educational content, such as quizzes and simulations.	0.67	0.503
11	there are AI being used to analyze and improve writing and grammar skills for college students.	0.79	0.524
13	there are platforms powered by AI that let college students access online tutoring and homework help.	0.56	0.540
14	AI-powered tools that help me create personalized study schedules and time management plans.	0.55	0.447
15	there are AI software tools used to detect and prevent plagiarism in student submissions.	0.66	0.506
16	there are AI-powered platforms that recommend relevant educational materials, such as textbooks and articles, based on my courses and interests.	0.48	0.536
19	artificial intelligence (AI) tools assist students in quickly locating relevant research materials.	0.41	0.407

Factor 4 examines the perceived benefits of AI-powered tools in an academic context. The results from the Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) indicate varying factor loadings, with higher values such as 0.69, 0.67, and 0.79 showing a strong association between these items and the underlying factor. These items significantly contribute to measuring the construct of perceived benefits. In contrast, lower factor loadings, such as 0.48 and 0.41, suggest weaker associations, indicating that these items may be less relevant or influenced by factors not captured in the analysis. The magnitude of these loadings should be evaluated alongside theoretical considerations to ensure meaningful interpretation.

The communalities for Factor 4 range from 0.348 to 0.536, reflecting the proportion of variance in each item explained by the factor. For example, communalities like 0.503 and 0.524 indicate that these items are well-accounted for by the factor, enhancing the reliability of the construct measurement. Generally, factor loadings above 0.30 signify a moderate to strong correlation, and their significance, combined with adequate communalities, ensures that the extracted factor effectively represents the intended concept. These findings highlight the robustness of Factor 4 in capturing the perceived benefits of AI-powered tools within academic settings.

Table 6. Factor correlation matrix of the item-reduced Questionnaire

	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3	Factor 4
Factor 1	1.0	-	-	-
Factor 2	0.70	1.0	-	-
Factor 3	-0.42	-0.34	1.0	-
Factor 4	0.69	0.56	-0.32	1.0

This table provides insights into the relationships among the extracted factors from the data. The factor correlation matrix reveals that the correlation within each factor (Factor 1, 2, 3, and 4) should not exceed 0.7 or be less than/equal to 0.7. Referring to the table of value, factors have both positive and negative correlation. Largest negative correlation: Factor 3 and Factor 4 with a correlation of -0.42. Smallest negative correlation: Factor 3 and Factor 2 with a correlation of -0.34. Largest positive correlation: Factor 2 and Factor 4 with a correlation of 0.56. Smallest positive correlation: Factor 3 and Factor 2 with a correlation of -0.32 therefore this indicates the strength and direction of linear relationship between two variables.

Table 7. Internal reliability of the factors of the item-reduced Questionnaire (35-item)

The table shows the reliability value of the factors in Cronbach's Alpha that assessed each factor's reliability and removed the items that affect the reliability factor.

Factor	Cronbach's Alpha
Factor 1 (Perception of AI Impact)	0.920
Factor 2 (Willingness to Adapt)	0.919
Factor 3 (Knowledge of AI-powered Tools)	0.820
Factor 4 (Perceived Benefits)	0.880

Pertaining to Table 4 for reliability value of the extracted question and measured question, Factor 1 (Perception of AI Impact) having the Cronbach's Alpha 0.920 exceeds 0.7 that means the factor reliabilities were therefore satisfied for CFA validation and same as to the other factors. Cronbach's Alpha was intent to reduce the number of questions by intercorrelating what the question measures while also considering the factor loading impact in omitting questions to increase the Alpha that would be able to identify the highest value to be considered as the factor/s. The Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) model constituted 35 extracted questions out of 70 initial pool of question as general.

CONFIRMATORY FACTOR ANALYSIS

Table 8. CFA Model 1 (N=483)

Fit Index	CMIN/DF	TLI	CFI	IFI	NFI	RMSEA
Value	2.391	0.896	0.903	0.904	0.846	0.054

The table shows the equivalent of how suitable the value is to undergo analysis. According to the table presented by Cucos (n.d.), the accepted fit of Chi-square divided by degrees of freedom (CMIN/DF*) is ≤ 3 which means an acceptable fit and ≤ 5 is a reasonable fit. Tucker-Lewis index (TLI*) usually lower than is the GFI (Goodness Fit Index) --but values over .90 or over .95 are still considered acceptable. In Comparative fit index (CFI*), 1 means perfect fit, ≥ 0.95 = Excellent fit and $\geq .90$ = Acceptable fit. Moss (2016) interpret Incremental Fit Index (IFI*) as $\geq .90$ is an acceptable fit, although this index can exceed 1. Moss (2016) supported that Normed Fit Index (NFI*) results in values between 0 and 1. The closer the NFI to 1, the better the fit. NFI values above 0.9 usually represent acceptable fit. Root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA*) ≤ 0.05 means reasonable fit.

Figure 2. Final Hypothesized CFA Model

Figure 2 presents the Final Hypothesized CFA Model, illustrating the strength of relationships between the latent variables through correlation values indicated by the arrows. The strength of each relationship between the latent variables is given by the correlation value that is established on every two head arrows (Sürücü, n.d.). To determine the significance of these relationships, the t-test is employed (Schumacker & Lomax, 2004).

Table 9. Final Hypothesized CFA Model

Fit Index	CMIN/DF	TLI	CFI	IFI	NFI	RMSEA
Value	1.735	0.945	0.951	0.951	0.892	0.039

The table describes the fit indices for the final hypothesized Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) model, assessing how well the model aligns with the observed data.

Conclusions

In analyzing the results, the collected data must undergo Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) to test its suitability for Factor Analysis. This means that we cannot undergo analysis if the KMO value does not fit.

In identifying factors, it is being analysed first using the Parallel Analysis to identify the significant principal components. The scree plot shows the eigenvalues that represent the red line and then each of that blue line above the red line signifies the factor to be extracted. Upon analyzing the data under Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA), the number of questions was being reduced to explore the underlying structure of the question. While in Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) analyze how accurate the measured variables are.

Out of the seventy (70) constructed general questions about Artificial Intelligence (AI), we have crafted thirty-five (35) questions and identified four (4) factors which is the Perception of AI Impact, Willingness to Adapt, Knowledge of AI-powered Tools, and the Perceived Benefits that gauge Central Mindanao University students' awareness towards Artificial Intelligence.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are made based on the findings and conclusion of the study.

This study has carefully developed a comprehensive questionnaire with thirty-five (35) items, providing a valuable tool for future researchers to measure the students' awareness towards artificial intelligence powered tools. This accomplished questionnaire may be useful for future researchers with the interest in delving into Awareness about AI-powered tools.

In terms of sample size, the researchers highly recommend considering a wide range of participants from the population. A larger sample size generally leads to more accurate and precise results, reducing the likelihood of errors or misleading conclusions.

By including a diverse range of individuals, the future researcher may obtain a more comprehensive understanding of the topic under investigation.

When it comes to gathering data, it would be advantageous for the researcher to have a backup plan in place. This backup plan would serve to address potential challenges that may arise, such as encountering low response rates or facing unexpected difficulties in accessing the intended sample. By providing a clearly outlined backup procedure, which details alternative methods or sources, the researcher may ensure that the desired number of participants is maintained. This approach ultimately enhances the reliability and completeness of the data collection process.

The timeframe of a study holds substantial influence over its scope and findings. Therefore, it is advisable for future researchers to carefully manage the timeframe to ensure comprehensive data collection and analysis, resulting in a more comprehensive understanding of the subject. However, it is important to note that adjusting the timeframe may introduce certain challenges. Factors such as changes in external circumstances or evolving research methods need to be considered, as they may impact the research outcomes. The decision regarding the timeframe should be based on the specific research objectives and the availability of resources.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study observed the following ethical guidelines; Informed consent, as defined by Faden & Beauchamp (1986), refers to a participant's independent approval. In this study, participants received detailed information about the study's goals, their rights, and their voluntary involvement. They have the choice to participate after understanding the study's purpose. Before responding to the survey, participants received a consent letter, aligning with principles of autonomy, beneficence, and justice.

Data privacy is an ethics that protects the privacy and personal information of the participants. The researchers pledge honesty, ensuring anonymity, confidentiality, and limited use of data solely for the study's purpose. Nguyen et al. (2022) emphasize the need to protect stakeholders' personal data, especially in the context of virtual learning, necessitating collective efforts and self-awareness from all involved parties.

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